

SYNTHESIS OF OXADIAZOLES, THIADIAZOLES AND TRIAZOLES: REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Many drugs are producing resistance to the various diseases. So, there is an urgent need to synthesize the new chemical entities with potent biological activity. This review may help the medicinal chemist to develop the new chemical entities with oxadiazole, thiadiazole and triazole as the heterocyclic nucleus with higher efficiency and less side effects. This review gives the information about the synthetic routes of the oxadiazole, thiadiazole and triazole.

Keywords: Oxadiazole, Thiadiazole, Triazole, Synthesis, Biological activities.

I. INTRODUCTION

The five membered heterocyclic rings containing oxadiazole, thiadiazole and triazole moieties exhibits variety of biological activities.¹⁻² The oxadiazole molecules act as spacer via coordination, hydrogen bonding and show intermolecular cooperative interaction. Oxadiazole derivatives, which belong to an important group of heterocyclic compounds, have been the subject of extensive study in the recent research. Numerous reports have highlighted their chemistry and use.³ Oxadiazole derivatives show diverse biological activities, such as anti-tuberculostatic, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antipyretic and anticonvulsant.⁴ Oxadiazoles are 5-membered heterocyclic fragment compounds consisting of one oxygen atom, two nitrogen atoms and two carbon atoms.⁵ Depending on the position of the nitrogen with inside the ring, numerous isomers exist together with 1,2,4; 1,2,5; 1,2,3; and 1,3,4-oxadiazole (Fig. 1).⁶ Various pharmacological activities such as antibacterial, anti-fungal, anticonvulsant, anticancer, antitubercular, antimicrobial as well as analgesic have been reported for this scaffold.⁷⁻⁸

Fig. 1 Isomers of Oxadiazoles

The derivatives of thiadiazoles, depending on the nature of substituents can be found as a structural fragment of drugs and herbicides with a wide spectrum of activity due to the presence of the toxiphobic -N=C-S- linkage.⁹ They are known as the carbonic anhydrase inhibitors and some of them possess antimycobacterial, anesthetic, antidepressant, anxiolytic, anti-inflammatory, anticonvulsant, antihypertensive and anticancer activities. They also find applications in agriculture, material chemistry and are also useful as corrosion inhibitors.¹⁰⁻¹³ Thiadiazole is a five membered ring system containing two nitrogen atoms, one sulphur, two carbon atoms in ring system.¹⁴ Thiadiazole is found in four forms 1,2,4-thiadiazole, 1,2,3-thiadiazole, 1,2,5-thiadiazole and 1,3,4-thiadiazole (Fig. 2).¹⁵ Various pharmacological activities such as antidiabetic, antimicrobial, anticancer, antitumor, anti-inflammatory, antitubercular as well as antiviral have been reported for this scaffold.¹⁶⁻¹⁸

Fig. 2 Isomers of Thiadiazoles

Triazoles and their derivatives represent an interesting class of heterocyclic compounds possessing a wide spectrum of biological activities. A large number of triazoles are known to exhibit bactericidal, fungicidal, antitubercular, analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antitumor, anticonvulsant, antiviral, insecticidal, antidepressant and central nervous system activities.¹⁹ Triazole is one of the classes of organic heterocyclic compounds

containing a five membered structure composed of three nitrogen atoms and two carbon atoms. Two isomers of Triazole are present these are as follows (Fig. 3):

Fig. 3 Isomers of Triazoles

Various pharmacological activities such as antibacterial, anticancer, anti-proliferative antitubercular, anti-inflammatory, antiviral, antifungal urease & lipase inhibitors, anti-tumour activity, antioxidant, anti-corrosive, hypoglycemic, anti-tyrosinase, anti-nociceptive, anti-convulsant, anthelmintic, anti-migraine, sedative, diuretic, muscle relaxant as well as anti- HIV have been reported for this scaffold.²⁰⁻²⁵

The research upon these three heterocycles is going on to get the new chemical entities. The synthesis of these three heterocycles is a very important task now a days. So, to make the work easy for new researchers we have made the review on the synthesis schemes of these three heterocycles. The various schemes were studied from various research papers and are combined in this review paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Synthesis of Oxadiazoles:

- Khanfara M. et.al., have reported that on heating 1-Isothiocyanato-4-methylbenzene at 65-80 °C for 1 hour with Hydrazine and MeOH gives 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. The formed 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (1.0 mol) is treated with acetic acid (1.0 mol) in presence of 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDCI) and Dichloromethane to get the desired product 5-methyl-N-m-tolyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-amine. The thiosemicarbazides were readily prepared by reacting the corresponding isothiocyanate with hydrazine under reflux in MeOH (Fig. 4).²⁶

Fig. 4 Synthesis of 5-methyl-N-m-tolyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-amine

- Ningegowda R. et.al. synthesized a series of derivatives for their anti-tubercular activity against Mycobacterium tuberculosis. The 2,3-dichlorobenzoic acid (131.60 mmol) is refluxed with MeOH (200 ml) and sulphuric acid to get methyl-2,3-dichlorobenzoate. The obtained benzoate is refluxed with Hydrazine hydrate and EtOH to get 2,3-dichlorobenzohydrazide. This 2,3-dichlorobenzohydrazide is reacted with any acid and Phosphoryl chloride (POCl₃) a cyclization agent at RT and the final product (Fig. 5) with oxadiazole ring is prepared i.e., 2-(2,3-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole.²⁷

Fig. 5 Synthesis of 2-(2,3-dichlorophenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole

- Yadava N. et.al. have reported the 4-(tert-butyl) benzo hydrazide (0.01 mol) reacted with CS₂ (2 ml) in presence with ethanol and potassium hydroxide (0.01 mol) 0 °C for 20 minutes and then refluxed for 4 hours until the H₂S is evolved. The obtained intermediate 5-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione was purified by column chromatography and further reacted with different amines in the presence of formaldehyde in anhydrous ethanol at RT to yield 5-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-3-((2,3,4-trimethylphenylamino)methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione (Fig. 6).²⁸

Fig. 6 Synthesis of 5-(4-tert-butylphenyl)-3-((2,3,4-trimethylphenylamino)methyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2(3H)-thione

- This synthesis was reported by Bhati S. et.al. where ethyl 2-(4-methylpiperazine-1-yl) acetate (0.01 mol) was reacted with dry acetone (0.02 mol) and K₂CO₃ (2 g) and ClCH₂COOC₂H₅ to get 2-(4-methylpiperazine-1-yl) acetohydrazide. 2-(4-methylpiperazine-1-yl) acetohydrazide was reacted with NH₂NH₂·H₂O and C₂H₅OH to get 1-methyl-4-((5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl) methyl) piperazine (Fig. 7).²⁹

Fig. 7 Synthesis of 1-methyl-4-((5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-yl) methyl) piperazine

- Caneschi W. et.al. reported synthesis of 5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol. First step involved refluxing of benzoic acid (0.1 mol) with concentrated sulphuric acid, EtOH, NH₂NH₂ (2.0 mol) for 20 hours to form benzohydrazide. This in the second step when heated at 55 °C for 48 hours with KOH, Ethanol and CS₂ (4.0 mol) formed the title compounds (Fig. 8).³⁰

Fig. 8 Synthesis of 5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole-2-thiol

- Following synthesis was performed by Zhanga Y. et.al., Benzoic acid (1.5 mol) and N-dihydroxy-1H-indol-5-carboxamide (2.0 mol) were reacted in presence of 1-Ethyl-3-(3-dimethylaminopropyl) carbodiimide (EDCI), Hydroxybenzotriazole (HOBT), N,N-Diisopropylethylamine (DIEA), Dimethylformamide (DMF) to obtained the oxadiazole derivative. The reaction conditions involved heating in microwave at 180 °C for 20 minutes (Fig. 9).³¹

Fig. 9 Synthesis of 6-(5-phenyl-1,2,4-oxadiazol-3-yl)-1H-indole

- Mansouri E. et.al., reported the synthesis of 1,3,4- oxadiazole homonucleosides and their double-headed analogs as antitumor agents. In the first step N-alkylation of theophylline (0.25 mol) is carried out using ethylbromoacetate (0.50 mol) in presence of excess of dimethylformamide (DMF) and potassium carbonate (K₂CO₃) to give ethyl 2-((1,3-dimethyl-1,2,6-dioxo-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropurin-7-yl) acetate. The intermediate formed is further reacted with Phosphoryl chloride (POCl₃) to get the product (Fig. 10).³²

Fig. 10 Synthesis of 7-((5-(chloromethyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methyl)-1,3-dimethyl-1H-purine-2,6(3H,7H)-dione

- Taha M. et.al. reported the synthesis of phenyl linked oxadiazole- phenylhydrazone hybrids (Fig. 11). By refluxing methyl-2-methoxybenzoate (0.3 mol) with Hydrazine (0.1 mol) for 6 hours 2-methoxybenzohydrazide was synthesized. The resulting 2-methoxybenzohydrazide was reacted with different aromatic aldehydes to yield hydrazone. Hydrazone upon oxidative cyclization with phenyliododiacetate (PhI(OAc)₂) in dry chloroform forms oxadiazole ring. Further it was converted into the phenyl linked oxadiazole-hydrazide hybrid by reacting with hydrazine hydrate.³³

Fig. 11 Synthesis of 4-(5-(2-methoxyphenyl)-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl) benzohydrazide

- Kumaraswamy B. et.al. reported the synthesis of derivatives of phenyl-oxadiazole hybrids. 4-fluorophenol (0.2 mol) is heated at 40-45 °C with acetyl chloride (0.01 mol) to get 4-fluorophenyl acetate. The prepared 4-fluorophenyl acetate is treated with AlCl₃ and MeOH at 140-145 °C to get 1-(5-fluorohydroxyphenyl)ethenone. The reaction takes place by one pot Friedel Craft acetylation followed by Fries rearrangement. The 1-(5-fluorohydroxyphenyl) ethenone is reacted with diethyl oxalate and MeOH in presence of Sodium methoxide at 65-70 °C gives ethyl-4-(5-fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-2,4-dioxobutanoate. Ethyl 4-(5-fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl)-2,4-dioxobutanoate is treated with hydrochloric acid at 85-90 °C acid catalyzed cyclisation is the mechanism of reaction. The formed product is then treated with acetic acid at 75-80 °C to get 6-fluoro-3,4-dihydro-2H-chromene-2-carboxylic acid. 6-fluoro-3,4-dihydro-2H-chromene-2-carboxylic acid is refluxed with MeOH and H₂SO₄ the 6-fluoro-3,4-dihydro-2H-chromene-carboxylate. This product is obtained by hydrogenation. By hydrazinolysis of ester hydrazides was obtained. The hydrazide is a key product for synthesis of 2,5-

disubstituted 1,3,4-oxadiazole by refluxing in Phosphoryl chloride with substituted aromatic carboxylic acid derivatives to afford final products (Fig.12).³⁴

Fig. 12 Synthesis of 2-(6-fluoro-3,4-dihydro-2H-chromen-2-yl)-5-phenyl-1,3,4-oxadiazole

• Chortani S. et.al. performed the synthesis of the quinazoline and oxadiazole hybrid derivatives. 2-Aminobenzamide (5 mmol) and Benzaldehyde (5 mmol) was reflux for 24 hours in the presence of dry Acetonitrile (50 ml) and Iodine. The formed intermediates 2-p-tolylquinazolin-4(3H)-one, 2-(4-oxo-2-p-tolylquinazolin-3-(4H)-yl) acetohydrazide and n-ethylidene-2-(4-oxo-2-p-tolylquinazolin-3(4H)-yl) acetohydrazide are treated with NH_2NH_2 , EtOH, $\text{ClCH}_2\text{COOEt}$. The resulted product 2-(4-oxo-2-p-tolylquinazolin-3(4H)-yl) acetohydrazide was reacted with EtOH to produce N-ethylidene-2-(4-oxo-2-p-tolylquinazolin-3(4H)-yl) acetohydrazide. The prepared product was reacted with K_2CO_3 and excess of Iodine in presence of DMSO to get the product (Fig. 13).³⁵

Fig. 13 Synthesis of 3-((5-methyl-1,3,4-oxadiazol-2-yl)methyl)-2-p-tolylquinazolin-4(3H)-one

2.2. Synthesis of Thiadiazoles:

• M. Soleiman-Beigi et.al., synthesized phenylamino-5-alkylthio-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole (Fig. 14).³⁵ In first step Phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.1 mmol) and carbon disulphide (0.3mmol) in dimethylformamide (2.0 ml) stirred for 15 min at RT. Then in step second resulting solution heated at 70 °C for 7 hr. In final step alkyl halide (1.2 mmol) and Et_3N added to hot solution of second step and obtained 2-phenylamino-5-alkylthio-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole monitored by TLC.

Fig. 14 Synthesis of 5-(methylthio)-N-phenyl-4,5-dihydro-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-amine

• M.T. Javid et.al. reported synthesis of 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (Fig. 15) derivative.³⁶ First step involved thiosemicarbazides (1 mol) and Benzaldehyde (1 mol) was refluxed with hydrochloric acid (2-3 ml) were refluxed with ethanol (10 ml) for 3-4 hours. In final step cyclization was done by iodine (0.1mol) and potassium carbonate (0.1mol) with 1,4-dioxane refluxed for 4 hours at 80 °C above mixture was cooled at RT and solid particle was collected.

Fig. 15 Synthesis of 2-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole

• Zongjie G. et.al. synthesized a series of 2-((5-((4-Chlorophenyl) amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) thione)-1-phenyl derivative (Fig.16).³⁷ It involved reaction of benzothiohydrazide (0.2 mol) and N, N-dimethyl acetamide (0.2 mol) with (0.01 mol) KHSO₄ which shows cyclization thiohydrazines acts as transamination or dehydrating agent which shows thiadiazole ring formation and obtained target compound.

Fig. 16 Synthesis of 2-((5-((4-Chlorophenyl) amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) thione)-1-phenyl

• Following synthesis performed by Halit M. et.al., to prepared N-arylthiadiazole derivative (Fig. 17).³⁸ Thiophene-3-carboxylic acid (0.2 mol) chilled in refrigerator with N-Aryl Semi thiocarbazine (0.2 mol) reacted with phosphorus oxychloride (0.02 mol) drop wise stirred 4 hours at 90 °C residue was filtered and washed synthesized thiadiazole derivative.

Fig. 17 Synthesis of N-arylthiadiazole

• Ahmet C. et.al., reported synthesis of 2-((5-((4-Chlorophenyl) amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) thione)-1-phenyl derivative (Fig. 18).³⁹ In first step hydrazine hydrate (0.1 mol) was mixed with 4-Chlorophenyl isothiocyanate (0.22 mol) in ethanol (40 ml) for 2 hours stirred in ice bath to obtained 4-(Chlorophenyl) hydrazinecarbothioamide. In second step mixture of above compound (0.02 mol) carbon disulphide (0.024 mol) added ethanol (40 ml) with sodium hydroxide (0.024 mol) refluxed for 4 hours. In last step 4-(Chlorophenyl)amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2-thiol (0.83 mmol) was reacted with 2-bromoacetophenone (0.83 mmol) and potassium carbonate (0.83 mmol) were stirred in acetone (10 ml) to obtained 2-((5-((4-Chlorophenyl) amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) thione)-1-phenyl derivative.

Fig. 18 Synthesis of 2-((5-((4-Chlorophenyl) amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl) thione)-1-phenyl

• Dilek M. et.al. synthesized a series of 4-(trifluoromethyl)phenylthiadiazole derivative. In that 4-(trifluoromethyl)phenylisothiocyanate (0.01 mol) is reacted with ethanol (30 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02

mol) stirred at room temperature for 4 hours to prepared 4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl thiosemicarbazides. The above mixture (0.01 mol) was dissolved with carbon sulphide (0.1 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.1 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) and refluxed for 10 hours prepared thiadiazole thiones (Fig. 19).⁴⁰

Fig. 19 Synthesis of N-(Aryl)-2-[[5-((4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)amino)-1,3,4-thiadiazol-2-yl]thio]acetamide

• Dilek M. et.al. reported synthesis of 4-nitrophenylthiadiazole derivative (Fig.20).⁴¹ 4-nitrophenyl isothiocyanate (0.1 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.2mol) mixed to prepared 4-(4-nitrophenyl) thiosemicarbazides. By ring closure reaction of 4-(4-nitrophenyl) thiosemicarbazides (1) synthesized 5-(4-nitrophenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2(3h)-thione. then finally reaction of 5-(4-nitrophenylamino-1,3,4-thiadiazole-2(3h)-thione with N-(alkyl/aryl)2chloroacetamide was stirred with acetone and potassium carbonate at room temperature for 8 hours filtered the solution and residue was thiadiazole derivative.

Fig. 20 Synthesis of 4-nitrophenylthiadiazole derivative

• X. Lv et.al. prepared quinazoline-4(3H)-one;1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b] [1,3,4] thiadiazole derivative. In first step Methyl 2-amino benzoate (2 mol) refluxed with formamide (10 ml) for 12-14 hours to obtained quinazolin-4-one. In second step it treated with bromo acetate with continuous stirring to prepare ester (3 mol). In third step ester treated with ethanol (50ml) and refluxed for 12 hours to prepared hydrazide. Then hydrazide dissolved with ethanol (60ml) and potassium hydroxide (20.0mol) forms intermediate, then in last step intermediate (1.0 mmol) reacts with ethanol (40 ml) and hydrazine hydrate (131.7 mol) then refluxed for 5 hours with phosphoric chloride to obtained quinazoline-4(3H)-one;1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b] [1,3,4] thiadiazole (Fig. 21).⁴²

Fig. 21 Synthesis of Quinazoline-4(3H)-one; 1,2,4-triazolo[3,4-b] [1,3,4] thiadiazole

• Khan S. A. et.al. reported synthesis of biphenyl-4yl thiadiazole derivative. First step involved biphenyl-4-ylacetic acid (0.026 mol) refluxed with Ethanol (100 ml) and sulphuric acid (2.7 ml) for 18-20 hours in water bath prepared ethylbiphenyl-4yl acetate. ethylbiphenyl-4yl acetate(0.1 mol) reacted with hydrazine hydrate(0.5 mol) in ethanol refluxed for12-15 hours prepared biphenyl-4yl hydrazide and then mixture of hydrazide (0.002 mol) and 2-methylthiocynate (0.002 mol) in ethanol refluxed on water bath and thiosemicarbazides. Thiosemicarbazides (0.004 mol) added in small portion to 30 ml of 2 % sodium hydroxide

refluxed for 12 hours concentrated under vacuum filtered the solid Biphenyl-4-yl thiadiazole derivative was prepared (Fig. 22).⁴³

Fig. 22 Synthesis of Biphenyl-4-yl-thiadiazole derivative

Charitos G. et al. synthesized 3,4 disubstituted 1,2,4 triazolo [3,4 - b] 1,2,4 thiadiazole derivative. In first step ethyl-2-(N, N- sulphomoyl)- 4-5dimethoxy-phenylacetate (0.01 mol) treated with hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in xylol allowed to react with carbon sulphoxide (0.015 mol) in mixture of potassium hydroxide (0.015 mol) in ethanol (150 ml) stirred for 20 hours to obtained 2-(N, N dimethyl sulfamoyl)-4-5 dimethoxy- phenyl acetyl hydrazine. After that this leads to ring closure with hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) and prepared 5[2-(N, N dimethyl sulfamoyl)-4-5-dimethoxybenzyl]-3-mercapto 4 amino-1,2,4 triazole. Resulted solution treated with further aromatic acid (0.01 mol) refluxed for 2 hours solid product filtered was 3,4 disubstituted 1,2,4 triazolo [3,4-b] 1,2,4 thiadiazole (Fig. 23).⁴⁴

Fig. 23 Synthesis of 3,4 disubstituted 1,2,4 triazolo [3,4 - b] 1,2,4 thiadiazole

2.3. Synthesis of Triazoles:

Following synthesis was performed by Lin S. et al., hydrazonoyl chlorides (5.0 mmol, 1.0 mol) was reacted with bubbled ammonia in presence of dioxane (2.9 ml) at 0 °C for 24 h to formed hydrazoamides which reacted with 2.0 mol of 2-chloroacetyl chloride and NEt₃ (5.0 mol) in toluene and refluxed for 5 h to yield methyl 5-(halomethyl)-1-aryl-1H-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxylate derivatives (Fig. 24).⁴⁵

Fig. 24 Synthesis of methyl 5-(halomethyl)-1-aryl-1H-1,2,4-triazole-3-carboxylate

Zhang Y., reported the synthesis of 5-(2-fluorophenyl)-4-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol. In the first step 2-fluorobenzoic acid, thionyl chloride and ethanol refluxed for 3 h to formed ethyl-2-fluorobenzoate then it reacted with hydrazine and ethanol to give 2-fluorobenzohydrazine again it reacts with phenyl isothiocyanate and ethanol refluxed for 3 h to form 1-(2-fluorobenzoyl)-4-phenylthiosemicarbazide. The intermediate formed was further reacted with sodium hydroxide and hydrochloric acid refluxed for 4 h. Then the solution of 5-(2-fluorophenyl)-4-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol (1 mmol) and anhydrous ethanol (10 ml), 4-substituted piperazine (1 mmol) and 37% formaldehyde (3 mmol) is prepared and solution was stirred at RT for 1-2 h to get the product (Fig. 25).⁴⁶

Fig. 25 Synthesis of 5-(2-fluorophenyl)-4-phenyl-4H-1,2,4-triazole-3-thiol

- Grytsaia O. et.al. reported the synthesis of N,3-diphenyl-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amines is done by reaction of benzoyl chloride (1 mol) with substituted anilines (1 mol) and aryl carbonyl isothiocyanate (1.1 mol) refluxed for 12 h to give N-(phenylcarbamothioyl) nicotinamides (1 mol) then it reacted with hydrazine hydrate (3 mol) and 1,4-dioxane (10 ml/1 mmol) at 0 °C. The reaction was stirred for 24–30 h at room temperature to get the product (Fig. 26).⁴⁷

Fig. 26 Synthesis of N,3-diphenyl-1H-1,2,4-triazol-5-amines

- Following synthesis was performed by Dewangan D. et.al., Potassium hydroxide solution at 0.15M, absolute ethanol (200 ml), and pyridyl-2-carbohydrazide 0.10 M were mixed and then reacted with carbon disulphide at 0.15M with ethanol, after dilution, agitation was applied for 12-16h. After 16h, 200 ml of dry ether was added to the resulting solution to form 5-(pyridine-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-thiol (Fig. 27).⁴⁸

Fig. 27 Synthesis of 5-(pyridine-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-thiol

- Beyzaei H. et.al. reported the synthesis of 1,2,4-triazole-3-thiones. The reaction of aryl hydrazides (1 mmol) and 4-nitrophenyl isothiocyanates (1 mmol) in the presence of Gly/potassium carbonate as a solvent to get carbothioamides. Condensation of intermediate carbothioamides to yield 1,2,4-triazole-3-thione derivatives occurred at a minimum temperature of 100 °C (Fig. 28).⁴⁹

Fig. 28 Synthesis of 5-(pyridine-3-yl)-4H-1,2,4-triazole-thiol

- Guillon C. et.al. reported the reaction of thiocarbonylhydrazide with substituted acids to give 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-(R1)-4H-1,2,4-triazole (0.50 mmol). The intermediate formed is further reacted with aldehyde, trans-cinnamaldehyde (1.16 mmol) solubilized in 4 ml of absolute ethanol or THF. The mixture was stirred and refluxed usually for 6 hours, and a solid precipitate was obtained. The flask was cooled down to RT, then put in the freezer (-20 °C) overnight. The precipitate was filtered and rinsed with cold ethanol (0.323 mmol, 64 %) or tetrahydrofuran to give the expected 4-(R2-imino)-3-mercapto-5-(R1)-4H-1,2,4-triazole (Fig. 29).⁵⁰

Fig. 29 Synthesis of 4-amino-3-mercapto-5-(R1)-4H-1,2,4-triazole

- Zhang W. et.al. reported the synthesis of 4-(2,4-dinitrobenzylideneamino)-5-m-tolyl-2H-1,2,4-triazole-3(4H)-thione reaction of benzoic acid with different substituted esters, which includes esterification, hydrazidation, salt formation, and cyclization. To obtained 4-Amino-5-Substituent-1,2,4-Triazole-3-Thione [82][83][84] (5mmol) was added to the solution of 2,4-dinitrobenzaldehyde (5 mmol) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml), the mixture was refluxed for about 4 h. The reaction mixture was left standing overnight and then filtrated to collect product (Fig. 30).⁵¹

Fig. 30 Synthesis of 4-(2,4-dinitrobenzylideneamino)-5-m-tolyl-2H-1,2,4-triazole-3(4H)-thione

- Osmanov V. et.al. reported that solution of 1-isoselenocyanato-3-methoxybenzene (20 mmol) in EtOH was added to the boiling solution of 2-(2-thienyl acetohydrazide (20 mmol). The reaction mixture was refluxed for 4h and cooled to 20°C. A precipitate of N-(3-methoxyphenyl)-2-(2 thienyl acetyl)-hydrazinecarboselenoamide was formed. Then it was added to the aqueous solution of KOH and boil for 5 h. After cooling the precipitate of 4-(3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-thienylmethyl)-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3- selone was obtained (Fig. 31).⁵²

Fig. 31 Synthesis of 4-(3-methoxyphenyl)-5-(2-thienylmethyl)-2,4-dihydro-3H-1,2,4-triazole-3- selone

III. CONCLUSION

Thiadiazole, oxadiazole, triazole, tetrazole have attracted considerable attention in the field of medicine due to their structural and biological properties. Due to possessing a great biological activities and importance in medicinal chemistry, this is quite important for synthesis and work on all derivatives. By the various method of synthesizing of these heterocycles in this review, it may help in preparing newer compounds and evaluate the activity for heterocycle which may use in almost type of diseases with high efficacy and lower side effect. This review may help planning of work for researcher.

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